

Regression Data Analysis of How Factors Influence Opportunities for Employment Creation in China

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Abstract:

This article aims to explain through regression data analysis, how some factors such as political, social, cultural and economic factors impact graduates students from China to self-employment. Total of two hundred sixteen (216) graduates students from China express their different opinion through structured questionnaires. Questionnaires are structured according to Linkert scale framework where Items are rated from 1 to 5 (1-5, the higher is the score, the greater its affect). Dependents and independents variables are subjects to cronbatch test of reliability. Results shown that independent variables referred to as political, economic, social and cultural factors have deep impact on opportunity for entrepreneurship in term of employment creation in China. We found that China focuses on economic strengths to influence opportunities for employment creation. Moreover, the value of Cronbach's alpha reliability test for data collected among graduate's students from China is 0,770. Friedman's chi-square analysis of variance is significant at a $p = 0.000$. Therefore, variables are significant and consistent for regression analysis.

Keywords: Employment Creation; Entrepreneurship; Employment Opportunity; Factors; Career Objective; Career Planning.

1. Introduction

Employment has a vital bearing on people's livelihoods. It is the fundamental prerequisite and basic approach for people to improve their lives. Unfortunately, the phenomena to be unemployed after been graduated is a customs in this 21st century. According to the ILO(International Labor Organization,2012), 160 million people in the world today are unemployed, and many more subsist on the margins of the economy or have jobs that do not provide them with adequate means to ensure their survival. Nearly 40 per cent of those without work are youths, and the levels of unemployment tend to be two to three times higher for this group than for the adults. In response, governments and international organizations have begun to search for more inclusive labor market interventions to address unemployment, particularly among youths. However, governments are also concerned that any new economic growth and development may not lead to an increase in employment opportunities. In the move from passive to active welfare and labor market policies, numerous methods have been implemented in order to tackle youth unemployment, ranging from public works, subsidized employment, vocational and basic skills training to increasing benefits sanctions on those outside the formal labor market. Increasingly, self-employment (SE) and support for entrepreneurial activities are seen as possible policy mechanisms by which to reduce unemployment, welfare dependency and poverty. However, the evidence base from a variety of economic contexts provides mixed results on the efficacy and effectiveness of these policies and interventions (ILO, 2015; working paper No. 198).

According to the statistics from China Scholarship Council, 2016, total international students enrollment in public and private institutions in 2015 is 397,635 and the number continue increasing each year. Each year, more and more graduates from foreign universities are coming to China with goal to build up career or to find decent job. In the context of the global economic slowdown, many of these international students in China are faced with a tough choice: stay in China or return to their motherland after graduation. China's economic development has also attracted many universities graduates from others countries. Moreover, every year, numerous college graduates from China are coming out from

Chinese universities themselves. Such prevalent situations increase the seriousness of the problems of unemployment in China.

Previous authors, listed some outcomes factors that has significant impact on opportunities for employment creation. for example, LI Liang-cheng, ZHANG Fang-yan(2012), in his empirical study of the Impact of Entrepreneurial Policy on College Students' Entrepreneurial Motivation ; South China University of Technology, Guangzhou Guangdong 510640,China; listed financial support, business support, entrepreneurship education, supporting measures and entrepreneurial culture as factors in entrepreneurial policy to impact college students entrepreneurial motivation in term of employment creation. N Nayab(2011) , the Hub for Bright Minds, in : “ Factors Having an Impact on Starting and Operating a Business”, Overviewed: The major factors that influence entrepreneurship. N Nayab(2011 show how cultural ,political, economic factors influence entrepreneurship. How availability of resources, psychological orientation and entrepreneurial skill affect entrepreneurship. Peter Senge(1990), in: “The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization Peter Senge(1990) books pulled together his extensive research into what different organizations do to build learning capacity and why some organizations use learning better than others. Although Senge does not gives directly the list of factors influence opportunity for employment creation, he does mentioned 5 Leadership Learning Disciplines with emphasize on learning skills to build a successful organization. For example on his page 285 (The Fifth discipline) he said: “related what O’Brien says: “I can practice all the analytical steps in the world toward openness, and it is not enough. If you have the fundamental Spiritual disposition, without the skill you will be ineffective. But in the other hand, if you develop the skill without the spiritual disposition, that won’t work fully either. He just underlines the importance to cultivate the right attitude of associating both spiritual dispositions with the skill, in order to lead successfully any business organization. Thus, Senge point out “Cultural Factor”, linking it with the skills the leader need to develop in order to successfully and build up organization.

LI Liang-cheng ZHANG Fang-yan (2012),N Nayab (2011) and Peter Senge (1990) listed factors such us Government policies and practices, Government supports regarding Taxes, infrastructures and utilities, favorable legislation, Human Capital, Population, Psychological Orientation, skills, knowledge, Believes, Perceptions, Behaviors, Preferences, Values, education, Business Opportunities; Firms and Institutions business practices; available resources; Incomes levels; Investment; Entrepreneurial opportunities to influence entrepreneurship to promote employment creation. We analyze such factors to explain what impact they do have on graduates’ students from China to self-employ.

We use Chi-square analysis of variance to measure the significance of variables. We collect data among 216 respondents, all from China. We analyze through regression data statistics method the impact of factors on graduates from China to self-employ. Results show that variables are correlated, consistent and significant. The value of Cronbach’s alpha reliability test for data collected among graduate’s students from China is 0,770. Friedman’s chi-square analysis of variance is significant at a $p = 0.000$. We ascertain that all variables are significant and consistent for data analysis.

2. Literature Review

Peter Senge(1990), in: “The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization pulled together his extensive research into what different organizations do to build learning capacity and why some organizations use learning better than others. He mentioned the 5 Leadership Learning Disciplines with emphasize on learning skills to build up a successful organization. For example on his page 285 (The Fifth discipline) he said: “related what O’Brien says: “I can practice all the analytical steps in the world toward openness, and it is not enough. If you have the fundamental Spiritual disposition, without the skill you will be ineffective. But in the other hand, if you develop the skill without the spiritual disposition, that won’t work fully either. He just underlines the importance to cultivate the right attitude of associating both spiritual dispositions with the skill, in order to lead successfully any business organization. Senge point out “Cultural Factor”, linking it with the skills the leader need to develop in order to successfully and build up organization.

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Bezanson & Hiebert(1997) , Lowe, Krahn, & Bowlby,(1997): “The transition from university to the world of work is defined as the process through which a student travels and set strategies and plans as well as relationship which can be defined and delineated. As a result of attention to this new horizon, it is possible to identify important new career education initiatives in Chinese universities and resources address student career opportunities and choices. several authors describe how , over the past decade, Chinese public policy initiatives have given new prominence to universities

career development practice and an agenda of improved career resources for Chinese fresh graduates. This situation is yet to be analyzed for foreign students enrolled in Chinese universities who seem not to be concerned by the Chinese public policy regarding employment reinforcement and career planning. For more comprehensive career achievement, the transition from school to work requires that the graduate students make personal and career choices within the framework of changing social and economic conditions”.

Hiebert et al (2001) asserted that the development of an effective and comprehensive guidance and counseling program begins with a comprehensive assessment of student needs. Gathering information directly from the students, not only helps to make the process of career planning more relevant for them, but it can help to ensure that students’ actual needs are taken into account in the formulation of the strategies (Hiebert et al 2001). For the perspective of understanding and supporting the career planning process of universities students, administration, teaching staff and other adults are the sources of information for program planning and tend to have the most influence on the career planning of the student (Hiebert et al 1998, Pyne et al 2002).

Universities students and fresh graduates are now challenged to develop specific and adequate knowledge and skills to pursue individual career goals (Alberta human resources and employment & Alberta learning, 1999; Dickson, 1995, human resources development Canada, 1998).

Anderson and Brown (1997) analyzed a set of 100 high school seniors. Among the sample, half attended high school in an urban area and half in rural areas. The objective of their research consisted of choosing participants to complete a packet containing career inventories, career decision making scales, and a demographic survey. Their results suggested that the higher one’s confidence in their ability to take on the career decision-making process the more likely they are to have a mature attitude toward career decision-making.

Patton and Creed (2001) also researched career maturity based on a sample of Australian adolescents ages 12 to 18 within the context of career development. The authors have administrated a career decision making scale and a career development inventory questionnaire to the sample and found that career maturity increased with age while career indecision seemed to increase in the senior year of high school.

3. Statement of Problem

The problematic of unemployment becomes a world-wide reality. In response, governments and international organizations have begun to search for more inclusive labor market interventions to address unemployment, particularly among youths. Increasingly, self-employment (SE) and support for entrepreneurial activities are seen as possible policy mechanisms by which to reduce unemployment, welfare dependency and poverty. Governments are also concerned that any new economic growth and development may not lead to an increase in employment opportunities. In the move from passive to active welfare and labor market policies, numerous methods have been implemented in order to tackle youth unemployment, ranging from public works, subsidized employment, vocational and basic skills training to increasing benefits sanctions on those outside the formal labor market. (ILO, 2015; working paper No. 198). In China, total international student enrollment in public and private institutions in 2015 is 397,635 and the number continue increasing each year (China Scholarship Council, 2016).

Each year, more and more graduates from foreign universities are coming to China with perspective to build career or to find job. In the context of the global economic slowdown, many of international students in China are faced with a tough choice: stay in China or return to their motherland after graduation. China's economic development has also attracted many universities graduates from others countries. Moreover, every year, numerous college graduates from China are coming out from Chinese universities themselves. Such prevalent situations increase the seriousness of the problematic of employment in China.

Facing today’s increasingly unemployment frequent situation, the need to develop a new approach of job creation or to analyze the old approach of the concept of employment creation is becomes serious. Thus, research procedures, practices and the relevant measures become primordial. Situations related to unemployment that prevailed in this current society and the efforts from China to face successfully and diligently the same phenomena leads us to undertake this study on factors influence opportunities for employment creation. We investigate on graduates students from China through regression statistics data analysis.

4. Objectives

Research objective is to explain how factors such as political, social, cultural and economic factors impact graduates students from China to self-employ.

5. Variables

This study analyzes some factors that influencing opportunities for decent job creation. Thus, the research dependent variables and independent variables are set according to LI Liang-cheng ZHANG Fang-yan (2012), N Nayab (2011),

Peter Senge (1990); And research dependent variables are determined on the basic of triangular principles of Action research developed by Matt Bond(August 2014) and on Bernardin, Russel (1993) illustrations as follow:

5.1. Independents Variables

Independents variables are determined based on the outcome factors listed by LI Liang-cheng ZHANG Fang-yan (2012), N Nayab (2011), and Peter Senge (1990). Independent variables for this part are determined as the factors that influence opportunities to promote employment creation in China, thus to create decent. Below are the items of political, social, cultural and economic factors:

Political Factors (Government policies and practices; Government supports; Taxes; Infrastructures and utilities; Favorable legislation)

Social Factors (Human Capital; Population; Psychological Orientation)

Cultural Factors (skills; knowledge; Believes; Perceptions; Behaviors; Preferences; Values; education)

Economic Factors (Business Opportunities; Firms and Institutions business practices; available resources; Incomes levels; Investment; Entrepreneurial opportunities).

5.2. Dependent Variables

Under previous empirical data analysis, we administrated a career decision making scale and career development inventory to the sample of graduates in China. One hundred two respondents participated actively. Addressing the kind of job respondents are looking forward and based on the response rates, highest of respondents 58%, prefer self-employment and the second highest rate of respondent, 42% prefer business than salaried job. Thus, results reveal that graduates in China, have a well define career planning strategy and career development. Therefore, we found that, graduates students with their career goal are in themselves an opportunities for employment creation. In conclusion, we determine research dependent variables as opportunity for employment creation with emphasize on self-career planning and self-career development as the main action for graduates to meet their goal.

6. Methodology and Research Design

Data are gathered, using questionnaires. We administrated Questionnaires structured according to Likert Scale frame to 216 respondents all from China. Respondents had the choice to complete the survey in Chinese language. A test given to 10 people was conducted to assure that the questions made sense to them in order to avoid any biases in the conducted study. We use Cronbach test of reliability to measure the consistency of variables. We use Chi-square analysis of variance to measure the significance of results obtained from data collected through questionnaire. Results, analysis and interpretations are presented below:

7. Data Analysis

Cronbach test is carried out to ascertain the relationship among dependents variables (opportunities for employment creation) and independents variables (political, economic, social and cultural) which have been examined in the current study. Particular attention was paid to the research in order to reduce the possibility of getting wrong answers, with focus to meet the reliability and validity requirements. The results of reliability and validity are presented bellow confirming thus the quality standards of the current research study. We use Cronbach test of reliability to measure the consistency of variables. We use Chi-square analysis of variance to measure the significance of results obtained from data collected through questionnaire. Average of variables factors (political, social, career planning, etc.) were calculate and use for the analysis.

7.1. Cronbach test of reliability scale: all variables

Reliability Statistics		
Table 1: Cronbach Test of Reliability		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.762	.770	39

The value of Cronbach's alpha reliability test for data collected among graduate's students from China is 0.770. Friedman's chi-square analysis of variance is significant at a $p = 0.000$. Thus, we assert that variables are significant to explain the impact of factors on the opportunity for employment creation.

Friedman chi-square for China

Table 2:ANOVA with Tukey's Test for Nonadditivity							
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig	
Between People		679.050	215	3.158			
Within People	Between Items	287.374 ^a	38	7.562	367.297	.000	
	Residual	Nonadditivity	12.711 ^b	1	12.711	16.962	.000
		Balance	6121.864	8169	.749		
		Total	6134.575	8170	.751		
	Total	6421.949	8208	.782			
Total		7100.999	8423	.843			
Grand Mean = 4.08							
a. Kendall's coefficient of concordance W = .040.							
b. Tukey's estimate of power to which observations must be raised to achieve additivity = 4.025.							

7.2. Regression Data Analysis: Data Collected Among China Graduates

- Career planning: independent variables n01

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on career objective (CO)

$$CO = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Table 3: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.493	1.100		1.357	.176
	Pol	.076	.188	.034	.402	.688
	S. F.	.000	.223	.000	.002	.998
	C. F.	.071	.224	.026	.318	.751
	E. F.	.375	.240	.115	1.563	.119****
<i>Dependent variable: CO</i>						
Note: *, **, ***, **** represent p = 0.01, 0.05, 0.1 And 0.2 respectively.						

$$CO = 1.493 + 0.076POL. + 0.071CF + 0.375EF$$

Result: It can be said that economic effect is significant at 20%. Which implies economic factor have impact on career objective of graduate in Asia. A unit point increase in economic factor increases graduate career objective by 0.375 points. Which can be inferred that the economic strength (i.e. strong or weak) in China have direct impact on graduate career objective.

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on career planning strategy (PS)

$$PS = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Table 4: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.078	.614		3.387	.001
	Pol	.171	.105	.134	1.628	.105***
	S. F.	.002	.124	.002	.019	.985
	C. F.	-.078	.125	-.051	-.628	.531
	E. F.	.340	.134	.184	2.539	.012*
Dependent Variable: PS						

$$PS = 2.078 + 0.171POL. + 0.002SF - 0.078CF + 0.340EF$$

Result: Economic and political factors are significant at 1% and 10% respectively as shown in the table above. Holding all factors constant a unit point increase in economic factor increases graduate career planning strategy by 0.340 points and that of political factor is 0.171. This implies both economic political factors have strong impact on graduate career planning strategies. Graduate who intend to start their own business should plan their career strategies having in mind that any improvement in the political gain and economics growth in China boost their future work.

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on future influence on current Plan (FIFP)

$$FIFP = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Table 5: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.400	.580		7.584	.000
	Pol	-.013	.099	-.011	-.126	.899
	S. F.	.149	.117	.109	1.269	.206****
	C. F.	-.214	.118	-.151	-1.811	.072***
	E. F.	-.043	.127	-.025	-.338	.736
Dependent variable: FIFP						

$$FIFP = 4.400 - 0.013POL. + 0.149SF - 0.214CF - 0.043EF$$

Result: In the future social factors have a positive influence graduate current career plans whilst that of cultural factors influence is negative. Social factor is significant at 20% and that of cultural is significant at 10%. A unit point increase in cultural factors decreases cultural future current plan of graduates. This is cultural values in China changes graduate career path. Which further means as Chines graduate known more about their culture their future plans concerning a

dream career is shape into another dream. Besides what is happening in the society positively shape graduate entrepreneurship plan.

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on career training (TtAFO)

$$TtAFO = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Table 6: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.266	.413		7.900	.000
	Pol	.052	.071	.061	.738	.462
	S. F.	-.001	.084	-.001	-.006	.995
	C. F.	-.136	.084	-.132	-1.614	.108***
	E. F.	.281	.090	.226	3.114	.002*

a. Dependent Variable: TtAFO

$$TtAFO = 3.266 + 0.052POL. - 0.001SF - 0.136CF + 0.281EF$$

Result: Cultural factors has a negative impact on career training whilst economic effect has a positive impact with 10% and 1% significance respectively. A unit increase in economic factor increase career training by 0.281. This suggest that as Chinese graduate receive career training they stand a chance of flourishing in their entrepreneurship quest as the Chinese economy flourishes. On the contrary cultural factor diminishes the economic gains. In sum, economic factors seem to affect most of entrepreneur career planning whilst political, social and cultural factor effect is minimal. This suggest entrepreneur in China stand a chance of flourishing so far as the economic indicators of China is on good standing.

Career Development: Dependents Variables N02

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on development of new skills (ODNS)

$$ODNS = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Tables 7: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.230	.874		2.552	.011
	Pol	.007	.149	.004	.049	.961
	S. F.	.259	.177	.125	1.462	.145****
	C. F.	-.037	.178	-.017	-.206	.837
	E. F.	.203	.190	.079	1.067	.287

Dependent variables: ODNS

$$ODNS = 2.230 + 0.007POL. + 0.259SF - 0.037CF + 0.203EF$$

Result: social factor is significant at 20%. That is entrepreneurs develop new skill in good social environment. A unit increment in social factor increase new skill development by 0.259 point. This also signifies happens in our social environment direct entrepreneur. Example the social media have transform how services are delivered in China.

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on job opportunity to develop career (OFCD)

$$OFCD = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Table 8: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.549	.913		3.888	.000
	Pol	-.033	.156	-.018	-.211	.833
	S. F.	-.036	.185	-.017	-.193	.847
	C. F.	.184	.186	.083	.988	.324
	E. F.	-.008	.199	-.003	-.042	.966
Dependent variable: OFCD						

$$OFCD = 3.549 - 0.033POL. - 0.036SF + 0.184CF - 0.008EF$$

Result: None of the factors impact on job opportunity to develop career.

The impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on recent training influencing future job (TRDS)

$$TRDS = X_1POL. + X_2SF + X_3CF + X_4EF + \varepsilon$$

Tables 9: Coefficients						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	4.661	.747		6.239	.000
	Pol	-.047	.128	-.031	-.368	.714
	S. F.	-.075	.151	-.043	-.498	.619
	C. F.	-.183	.152	-.100	-1.206	.229
	E. F.	.202	.163	.091	1.237	.217
Dependent variable: TRDS						

$$TRDS = 4.661 - 0.047POL. - 0.075SF - 0.183CF + 0.202EF$$

Result: None of the factors impact recent training influence of entrepreneur future job. Meaning whatever training an entrepreneur receives now under any factor does not determine their future work.

8. Conclusion

In summary, results of regression data analysis with data collected among graduates from China reveal that China relies on economic strengths to promote employment creation. Economic factor remain the strongest items to influence graduates from China to self-employ. The regression data analysis of the impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on graduates Career Objective (CO) show that economic effect is significant at 20% (table 3). Which implies economic factor have impact on career objective of graduate in Asia. A unit point increase in economic factor increases graduate career objective by 0.375 points. Which can be inferred that the economic strength (i.e. strong or weak) in China have direct impact on graduate career objective.

Regression analysis of political, cultural, social and economic factors impacts on graduates career planning strategy (PS) show that economic and political factors are significant at 1% and 10% respectively as shown in table 4. Holding all factors constant a unit point increase in economic factor increases graduate career planning strategy by 0.340 points and that of political factor is 0.171. This implies both economic political factors have strong impact on graduate career planning strategies. Graduates who intend to start their own business should plan their career strategies having in mind that any improvement in the political gain and economics growth in China boost their future work.

Regression analysis of political, cultural, social and economic factors impacts on graduates' future influence on current plan (FIFP) show that in the future, social factors have a positive influence on graduate current career plans (table 5). However, cultural factors influence is negative. Social factor is significant at 20% and that of cultural is significant at 10%. A unit point increase in cultural factors decreases cultural future current plan of graduates. This is cultural values in China changes graduate career path. Which further means as Chinese graduate known more about their culture their future plans concerning a dream career is shape into another dream. Besides what is happening in the society positively shape graduate entrepreneurship plan.

Regression analysis of the impact of Political, Cultural, Social and economic factors on career training (TtAFO) shows that cultural factors has a negative impact on career training while economic effect has a positive impact with 10% and 1% significance respectively. A unit increase in economic factor increase career training by 0.281. This suggest that as Chinese graduate receive career training they stand a chance of flourishing in their entrepreneurship quest as the Chinese economy flourishes. On the contrary cultural factor diminishes the economic gains. In sum, economic factors seem to affect most of entrepreneur career planning while political, social and cultural factor effect is minimal. This suggest entrepreneur in China stand a chance of flourishing so far as the economic indicators of China is on good standing.

Regression analysis of the impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on Development of New Skills (ODNS) shows that social factor is significant at 20%. That is entrepreneurs develop new skill in good social environment. A unit increment in social factor increase new skill development by 0.259 point. This also signifies that what happens in our social environment direct entrepreneurs. Example the social media have transform how services are delivered in China.

Regression analysis of the impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on Job Opportunity to develop career (OFCD) shows that none of the factors impact on job opportunity to develop career.

Regression analysis of the impact of political, cultural, social and economic factors on Recent Training Influencing Future Job (TRDS) shows that none of the factors impact recent training influence of entrepreneur future job in China. Meaning whatever training graduates as an entrepreneur receives now under any factor does not determine their future work. In conclusion, factors such as political, social, cultural and economic factors impact positively graduates students from China to self-employ with focus on economic strengths of China to boost employment.

9. References

- [1] ILO, (2007a). Rapport du Forum de l'OIT sur le Travail Decent au service d'une mondialisation equitable. Lisbonne, Portugal 31 octobre-2 novembre 2007.
- [2] ILO, (2007b). Activites de l'OIT en Afrique, 2004-2006. Rapport du Directeur General Onzieme Reunion. regionale africaine Addis-Abeba, Ethiopie, avril 2007.
- [3] Bezanson, L., & Hiebert B (1997) Career development in Canada: An emerging national strategy. In R. Feller & G. Waltz (Eds.), Career development in turbulent times: Exploring work, learning and careers. Greensboro, NC: ERIC/CASS
- [4] Hiebert, B., S. Collins, and J. Robinson. "Needs Assessment for Program Planning and Program Development: A Brief Review." Alberta Counsellor 26, 1 (2001): 11-26.

- [5] LI Liang-cheng, ZHANG Fang-yan(2012):” empirical study of the Impact of Entrepreneurial Policy on College Students' Entrepreneurial Motivation ; South China University of Technology , Guangzhou Guangdong 510640,China.
- [6] N Nayab(2011) , the Hub for Bright Minds: “ Factors Having an Impact on Starting and Operating a Business”.
- [7] Peter Senge(1990): “The Fifth Discipline: The Art and Practice of the Learning Organization.
- [8] Kamer, Pearl M. (2005), the Economic Impact of Brookhaven National Laboratory on the New York State Economy. Report prepared for the Brookhaven National Laboratory.
- [9] Kammen, Daniel M., Kamal Kapadia, and Matthias Fripp.(2006) Putting Renewables to Work: How Many Jobs Can the Clean Energy Industry Generate? RAEL Report, University of California, Berkeley.